

SCENARIOS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A 4G/5G BASE STATION USING THE SRSRAN SOFTWARE AND THE USRP RADIO MODULE

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Characteristics of the software layer

- srsEPC – full stack 4G Core:
 - MME (Mobility Management Entity)
 - HSS (Home Subscriber Server)
 - S-GW (Serving Gateway)
 - P-GW (Packet Data Network Gateway)
- srsENB – 4G (eNodeB)/5G NSA/5G SA (gNodeB) base station:
 - L1 level layer (Physical)
 - L2 level layers (MAC/RLC/PDCP)
 - L3 level layers (RRC/S1-AP (control) & GTP-U (data))
- srsUE – emulation of User Equipment with use of USRP Radio module

EPC Software Core structure

- Emulation of virtual network interface (TUN interface)
- Single file database in HSS module – quick management of authorized terminals using .csv format file
- Running in the Linux Command Terminal
- Possibility of capturing data from S1-AP and NAS protocol layer (with Wireshark use - .pcap file)

srsENB module – supported protocol stack

- Supporting FDD transmission mode
- Supporting 4G/5G NSA/5G SA mode (changing cell parameter)
- Supporting 2x2 MIMO modes (transmit diversity, cyclic delay diversity – CDD, closed loop spatial multiplexing)
- Bandwidth: 1.4, 3, 5, 10, 15, 20 MHz (4G mode) & 10 MHz (5G mode only)
- GUI environment – for monitoring PUSCH and PUCCH channels

srsUE – overall specification

- Possibility of configure fixed TX gain – automatic gain control not supported
- Configure the class of UE terminal (for class 8 – 64 QAM modulation scheme supported)
- TDD and FDD mode support
- Software and Hardware USIM supported (after connection of USIM PC/SC card reader) – virtual IMSI number emulation
- MIMO 2x2 or Carrier Aggregation mode
- 4G/5G full support
- Supported bandwidth – 1.4, 3, 5, 10, 15, 20 MHz

Hardware layer characteristics

- Frequency range (carrier): 70 MHz – 6 GHz
- MIMO 2x2 operation
- Up to 56 MHz continuous bandwidth
- 2 radio channels (on hardware single integrated daughterboard – USRP B210/E320)
- Variable master clock rate
- Ubuntu – based platform PC required for srsRAN

USRP B-210

USRP E-320

UHD channel mapping and USRP RF Frontend tuning process

- General carrier frequency tuning – realized by local oscillator
- DSP fine tuning – realized by FPGA module

$$b_{min} = lo_{freq} - masterclk_{freq}/2$$
$$b_{max} = lo_{freq} + masterclk_{freq}/2$$

- Basic scheme for UHD driver channel mapping:

$rx_subdev_spec = A:o B:o$

$tx_subdev_spec = A:o B:o$

A – daughterboard number

o – frontend number (RF port)

- USRP E320 channel mapping:

$rx_subdev_spec = A:o A:1$

$tx_subdev_spec = A:o A:1$

- USRP B210 channel mapping:

$rx_subdev_spec = A:A A:B$

$tx_subdev_spec = A:A A:B$

Basic issues and problems connected with 4G/5G USRP radio module implementation

- Channel mapping problem – USRP modules with one physical daughterboard (B210, E320 models) doesn't support 5G NSA. There's possible to use one RF port – 5G NSA requires two carriers on two RF ports
- Local Oscillator sharing problem – USRP B210 and USRP E320 have two configurable oscillators. In 5G NSA FDD mode there's need to generate two independent TX RF carriers – then one local oscillator is shared by both RX channels and second oscillator is assigned for TX channels – there is not possible to generate four independent frequencies by oscillator tuning
- Multi – USRP function don't support USRP B210 and E320 devices – not possible to split two devices into one logical radio module
- USRP N210 – not supported by srsENB – problem with input initialization arguments (time source mode error)
- USRP 1 – too narrow bandwidth – 5G mode requires 10 MHz bandwidth channels. USRP 1 can generate 8 MHz maximum bandwidth per channel

Implementation of the 4G base station system

srsUE operation

Commercial UE operation

Configuration of the 4G station

- 20 MHz bandwidth (per channel)
- MIMO operation (mode 4 – closed loop spatial multiplexing)
- AGC RX Control enabled in eNodeB & srsUE
- TX Fixed Gain: 100 dB
- UE class terminal: 8 category
- USRP B-210 (in eNodeB & srsUE)
- Xiaomi Redmi Note 10 5G (for Commercial UE)
- Ubuntu 22.10
- UHD v4.4.0
- PC class computers in eNode B & srsUE (AMD Ryzen 5 3600 processor, Nvidia Geforce GTX 1650, 16 GB RAM)

4G network performance measurements - srsUE

Iperf performance test - srsUE

4G network performance measurements - Commercial UE

Iperf performance test – Xiaomi Redmi Note 10

Radio channel power measurements

Power measurements – Downlink – 3,2 m - Xiaomi Redmi Note 10

	10 MHz SISO	20 MHz MIMO 4 AGC	20 MHz MIMO 4 100 dB	20 MHz MIMO 4 120 dB
10 cm - eNB - Idle mode	-61	-50	-44	-39
30 cm - eNB - Idle mode	-69	-65	-56	-58
10 cm - UE - Idle mode	-73	-66	-66	-70
10 cm - eNB - Active transmission	-51	-41	-31	-31
30 cm - eNB - Active transmission	-59	-56	-50	-49
10 cm - UE - Active transmission	-65	-67	-60	-61

— 10 cm - eNB - Idle mode
— 10 cm - UE - Idle mode
— 30 cm - eNB - Active transmission

— 30 cm - eNB - Idle mode
— 10 cm - eNB - Active transmission
— 10 cm - UE - Active transmission

Radio channel power measurements

Power measurements - Uplink - Active transmission - Xiaomi Redmi Note 10

	10 MHz SISO	20 MHz MIMO 4 AGC	20 MHz MIMO 4 100 dB	20 MHz MIMO 4 120 dB
10 cm - eNB - 3,2 m distance	-59	-52	-63	-53
30 cm - eNB - 3,2 m distance	-61	-54	-66	-61
10 cm - UE - 3,2 m distance	-40	-40	-42	-38
10 cm - eNB - 7,8 m distance	-65	-61	-60	-63
30 cm - eNB - 7,8 m distance	-66	-64	-60	-65
10 cm - UE - 7,8 m distance	-31	-31	-31	-38

- 10 cm - eNB - 3,2 m distance
- 30 cm - eNB - 3,2 m distance
- 10 cm - UE - 3,2 m distance
- 10 cm - eNB - 7,8 m distance
- 30 cm - eNB - 7,8 m distance
- 10 cm - UE - 7,8 m distance

Conclusions

- Increasing the radio channel width from 10 to 20 MHz increases the link speed by about 25% of the capacity
- Activation of the multi-antenna transmission mode did not cause a significant increase in transmission speed, but increased its stability
- Activation of the AGC mode (automatic receiving gain control) caused a decrease in bit rate due to the achievement of a lower gain than previously defined, which is associated with a decrease in the SNR value
- Exceeding the amplification value above 100 dB does not cause a significant increase in the transmission speed, which is related to the saturation of the radio module power stages

References

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Thank you for your attention